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Research article

Study On the Validity Of Instant Photography Method For Dietary Assessment In Undergraduate College Students

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Abstract:

Background A healthy diet in a college student life is critical to ensure their normal growth, study and development.

Aim In order to accurately assess the dietary pattern of college students and guide it, our study aims to evaluate the validity of instant photography as an alternative dietary assessment method in college students.

Methods Nine participants were enrolled and given a presentation on dietary assessment methods, including weighing, 24-hour recall, and instant photography. The participants took pictures of their foods from three angles before and after eating for constant seven days, foods weighing was completed by others. Then, the participants recalled the foods' weights after 24 hours. Two trained observers estimated food weight from the digital images (n = 285) gathered at the end of the study with the aid of Chinese food atlas reference.

Results Instant photograph showed significant correlation with weighing method on food weights of grains, tubers, vegetables, fruits, meat and eggs (all $P \leq 0.01$). 24-hour method had similar correlation with weighing method on food weights except fruits. Compared with 24-hour recall, instant photograph displayed underestimation on weights of grains, tubers, vegetables, and meat. However, instant photograph had more accurate estimations on weights of fruits and egg. Furthermore, compared with nutrients data from weighing method, both instant photography and 24-hour recall methods showed promising estimations on the amounts of energy, protein, fat, carbohydrate, vitamin A, vitamin C, vitamin E, calcium, iron and zinc (all $P < 0.001$). Compared with 24-hour recall, instant photograph displayed underestimation on the amounts of energy, protein, fat, carbohydrate, vitamin A, vitamin C, vitamin E, zinc. However, instant photograph had a more accurate estimation on calcium.

Conclusion Instant photography is an easy and feasible dietary assessment method for college students, with valid estimations.

Key words dietary assessment; instant photography; weighing method; 24-hour recall method; validity.

INTRODUCTION

College students will undergo regular physical examination when entering university or starting each semester. However, these examinations don't include dietary and nutritional assessment, except for weight and height measurement. A healthy diet in early adulthood is critical because literature has highlighted its association with current and future health [1-4]. If their dietary intake could be investigated during physical examination, an individualized suggestion could be provided, and the undergraduates can be urged to improve poor eating habits and maintain adequate and balanced nutrients intake. This initiative will have a lasting impact on their health in the future.

Diverse conventional methods of dietary assessment are available, such as weighing food, 24-hour recall, and food frequency questionnaires. Yet, these conventional methods are not ideal for the undergraduate population. The weighing food method is currently the gold standard of dietary assessment [5]. Basically, foods data are recorded before and after consumption. However, this method is time-consuming and burdensome to participants and researchers, making it inconvenient for conducting dietary surveys in large sample size. As for the 24-hour recall method and food frequency questionnaire, there is an extensive dependence on the recent memory of the study subjects [6]. Also, the capacity to accurately estimate the food depends on the interviewer ability in describing the ingredients, food preparation, and dishes. Because dietary assessment instruments depend on self-reporting, they are subject to substantial error, both random and systematic. In addition, several studies demonstrate a tendency towards underreporting and foods may also be forgotten with or without intention in student population [7]. If there is a convenient and appropriate method, it would be ideal to investigate dietary intake and habit along with the regular physical examination for undergraduates.

Instant photography as an alternative may help improve the flaws in conventional dietary assessment methods. This approach involves participants taking pictures of what they are going to eat before and after consumption. Studies have shown good compliance with youngsters in electronic data collection of dietary records [8]. Instant photography method is less time consuming, can be easily incorporate into the daily routine since all of youngsters have smartphones or other smart devices. It's highly economical and allows data collection in real time [6,9]. In addition, the digital photography method also displays good inter-agreement between trained observers [10]. Studies using digital photography methods have indicated valid and consistent results for children, while the food in this study was limited to sandwich [11]. Thus, the aim of this study is to evaluate the validity of the instant photography method for dietary assessment on routine foods in college students.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

SUBJECT AND DATA COLLECTION

This study was carried out on the Shipaiqiao Campus of Jinan University, Guangzhou city from Sept. 26, 2017, to Oct. 2, 2017. We recruited 9 healthy medical students, in their 5th year with good compliance. This study protocol conformed to the ethical guidelines of the 1975 Declaration of Helsinki. All eligible participants provided written, informed consent as approved by the Human Research and Ethics Committee of The First Affiliated Hospital, Jinan University. Before starting with the research, investigated students were given a presentation on how to complete different methods in this study. Two estimators were trained for a total of 10 hours following the "Chinese atlas of food" until a good agreement of estimation was reached.

WEIGHING FOOD

Weigh the food before eating. The investigated students asked any other person (roommate or classmates) to weigh every kind of food, and then recorded the name and corresponding weight of every kind of food. During the weighing process, the investigated subjects were asked to be out of touch with the data.

DIGITAL PHOTOGRAPHY

Before the research, a digital scale and a background paper printed with grid lines of a 1 cm × 1 cm and obvious border of 50 cm × 38 cm were handed to the subjects. The purpose of background paper was to serve as a reference when estimating the amount of food on the subject plates. After weighing, the students should capture pictures from 3 dimensions (45° of the front and 45° of the back and the top of the food), shown in Figure 1. The borders of the background paper should be included; if the food is too much, they can shoot it separately. Lastly, students shot the remaining food after eating if any, recorded and named the pictures. Subjects used their own phone to capture different meals. All of them used the same brand of phone (iPhone 6 or 6s). The acquired weights are cooked weight except that of the fruits.

Fig. 1 A typical example of digital photography in our study.

24 HR RECALL

All investigated students performed 24-hour recall by themselves separately and recorded the time, name and weight of every kind of food; the estimated weights are cooked weight except that of the fruits.

The whole process of data collection among the three methods was independent. At the end of the study, all of the photographed food data records were forwarded to the two estimators for objective estimation according to the Chinese food atlas reference. Chinese food atlas reference was designed by Professor Zhixu Wang from Nanjing medical university in China. Common foods were divided into 5-6 weight ranges (25g, 50g, 75g, 100g, 125g, 150g), and each portion food was cooked and placed on the tableware. Each cooked portion food was then pictured according to the methods of digital photography as the reference. The Chinese food atlas reference includes 7 kinds of grains, potato, and beans, 31 kinds of vegetables, 5 kinds of fruits, 5 kinds of livestock and poultry meat, 14 kinds of fish and seafood, 3 kinds of egg, 4 kinds of soybean and products.

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

Spearman correlation was used to assess the correlation of food weight and nutrients amount among three different methods. We calculated the estimated weight difference (d), absolute estimated weight difference (D), and the rates of these two ($d\%$, $D\%$). d = estimated weight - actual weight by weighing method, $D = |d|$, $d\% = d / \text{actual weight by weighing method} \times 100\%$, $D\% = D / \text{actual weight by weighing method} \times 100\%$. If the data were non-normal distributed, they were expressed as the median (interquartile range), Wilcoxon rank sum test was used to

compare the differences. All statistical analyses were performed using SPSS 21.0 and were considered statistically significant when $P < 0.05$.

RESULTS

BASIC INFORMATION

All of our nine participants were medical students of Jinan university aged between 20-24 y, all within normal BMI range (18.5-24.0 kg/m²) without any specific diseases or conditions. Each of them had at least 2 meals per day. Each meal was recorded by weighing food, 24-hour recall and instant photography methods for seven consecutive days. None of them dropped out from the study. Totally, there were 285 valid food data and 66 kinds of food collected.

Food items were grouped into six categories: 1. grains: $n = 15$ (rice, porridge, toast, bun, corn, udon, shortbread, doughnut, noodles, black rice, red rice, brown rice, cake, bread, spaghetti); 2. tubers: $n = 4$ (sweet potato, potato, yam, Chinese yam); 3. vegetables: $n = 30$ (pickled Chinese cabbage, pumpkin, Chinese cabbage, rape, lettuce, agaric, wax gourd, long bean, celery, bitter melon, Indian lettuce, Pleurotus geesteranus, cauliflower, cucumber, pepper, pickled, yellow turnip, onion, tuber mustard, Shanghai cabbage, broccoli, tomato, sweet potato leaves, water spinach, okra, eggplant, needle mushroom, pea, lotus root, flowering cabbage); 4. fruits: $n = 8$ (Yuzu, red grapes, apple, Psidium guajava, pineapple, Prune, kiwi fruit, pitaya); 5. meat: $n = 8$ (shrimp, pork, sardine, chicken, freshwater fish, beef, duck, tuna); 6. egg: $n = 1$ (eggs).

THE CORRELATION AND COMPARISON BETWEEN WEIGHING FOOD DATA WITH 24-HOUR RECALL AND INSTANT PHOTOGRAPHY

Each of the food item was estimated from instant photograph, 24-hour recall, and weighing records, shown in Table 1. Instant photograph showed significant correlation with weighing methods on food weights of grains, tubers, vegetables, fruits, meat and egg (all $P \leq 0.01$). 24-hour recall showed similar correlation with weighing method on food weights except fruits. Both instant photography and 24-hour recall displayed satisfactory estimations for tubers, vegetable and egg ($r > 0.7$).

Table 1 Correlation of food data on 24-hour recall and instant photography with weighing method.

Food type	n	24-hour recall		Instant photograph	
		r	p	r	p
All foods	285	0.760	< 0.001	0.755	< 0.001
Grains	77	0.656	< 0.001	0.763	< 0.001
Tubers	14	0.896	< 0.001	0.859	< 0.001
Vegetables	98	0.729	< 0.001	0.724	< 0.001
Fruits	11	0.340	0.306	0.736	0.010
Meat	67	0.776	< 0.001	0.676	< 0.001
Egg	18	0.866	< 0.001	0.712	0.001

Comparisons on food weight differences of 24-hour recall and instant photography with the weighing method are detailed in Table 2. Compared with 24-hour recall, instant photography displayed significant underestimations (indicated by d%) on grains (-9.5 (-26.6,17.6) vs. -18.2 (-31.1, -2.35), $P < 0.05$), tubers (-9.3 (-28.5, -2.80) vs. -22.4 (-54.2, -4.25), $P < 0.05$), vegetables (-12.1 (-29.5, 15.3) vs. -46.9 (-60.5, -30.5), $P < 0.001$), and meat (22.6 (-3.26, 54.8) vs. -31.5 (-53.0,

-4.36), $P < 0.001$). However, instant photograph had more accurate estimations (indicated by d%) on fruits (-16.1 (-26.7, -2.15) vs. 4.17 (-21.7, 29.5), $P < 0.05$) and egg (21.5 (10.2, 40.6) vs. 3.62 (-5.65, 25.2), $P < 0.01$). The weight difference of egg in instant photography (indicated by D) was significantly lower than that in 24-hour recall (10.3 (5.68, 17.3) vs. 8.9 (5.15, 16.3), $P < 0.01$ indicated by D).

Table 2 Comparison on food weight differences of 24-hour recall and instant photography with weighing method.

Type	n	Methods	d/g	D/g	d%	D%
All foods	285	24-hour recall	-1.01 (-22.4, 16.4)	19.4 (8.90, 37.0)	-0.99 (-23.2, 27.2)	25.7 (14.2, 47.7)
		Instant photography	-19.1 (-46.4, -2.60)***	27.4 (10.1, 50.3)***	-28.7 (-52.5, -3.90)***	37.1 (19.1, 53.9)***
Grains	77	24-hour recall	-8.4 (-30.5, 17.3)	24.4 (9.65, 56.8)	-9.50 (-26.6, 17.6)	24.1 (11.8, 43.5)
		Instant photography	-15.0 (-41.8, -2.30)*	23.7 (9.55, 43.7)	-18.2 (-31.1, -2.35)*	22.2 (11.1, 36.9)
Tubers	14	24-hour recall	-15.8 (-32.0, 1.04)	17.2 (8.11, 32.0)	-9.30 (-28.5, -2.80)	16.2 (7.19, 28.6)
		Instant photography	-18.1 (-45.0, -0.44)	27.5 (15.5, 90.9)*	-22.4 (-54.2, -4.25)*	37.3 (18.6, 54.2)*
Vegetables	98	24-hour recall	-36.1 (-63.7, -11.5)	17.5 (8.59, 36.5)	-12.1 (-29.5, 15.3)	26.3 (14.7, 44.2)
		Instant photography	-9.05 (-25.6, 8.82)***	37.5 (15.8, 65.1)***	-46.9 (-60.5, -30.5)***	49.6 (37.1, 60.5)***
Fruits	11	24-hour recall	-28.7 (-54.6, -3.30)	35.4 (24.1, 74.4)	-16.1 (-26.7, -2.15)	22.1 (13.6, 48.2)
		Instant photography	6.00 (-33.3, 68.4)*	39.6 (24.6, 68.4)	4.17 (-21.7, -29.5)*	24.7 (15.9, 31.9)
Meat	67	24-hour recall	11.1 (-1.20, 28.1)	18.3 (9.30, 32.1)	22.6 (-3.26, 54.8)	31.7 (14.4, 55.3)
		Instant photography	-17.5 (-36.2, -1.90)***	25.5 (9.20, 47.5)**	-31.5 (-53.0, -4.36)***	45.7 (22.3, 58.9)*
Egg	18	24-hour recall	8.90 (5.15, 16.3)	10.3 (5.68, 17.3)	21.5 (10.2, 40.6)	21.5 (10.2, 40.6)
		Instant photography	2.45 (-2.25, 7.25)***	8.90 (5.15, 16.3)**	3.62 (-5.65, 25.2)**	9.69 (4.10, 30.6)

Data are expressed as median (interquartile range) according to the distribution of variables. * $P < 0.05$, ** $P < 0.01$ and *** $P < 0.001$ when compared with 24-hour recall method.

THE CORRELATION AND COMPARISON BETWEEN WEIGHING NUTRIENTS DATA WITH 24-HOUR RECALL AND INSTANT PHOTOGRAPHY

Nutrients components of each food were estimated from the instant photography, 24-hour recall and weighing methods. As shown in Table 3, the correlations between instant photography and weighing method were similar to correlations between 24-hour recall and weighing method in all nutrients. Both instant photography and 24-hour recall showed good and valid estimations in energy, protein, fat, carbohydrate, vitamin A, vitamin C and zinc ($r > 0.7$). Furthermore, good and valid estimations for instant photography were displayed with vitamin E, calcium and iron. Comparisons on nutrients differences of 24-hour recall and instant photography with the weighing method are detailed in Table 4. Compared with 24-hour recall, instant photography displayed underestimations (indicated by d%) on energy (0.01 (-25.7, 27.6) vs. -29.75 (-56.9, 0.98), $P < 0.001$), protein (8.11 (-21.7, 12.2) vs. -26.5 (5.15, 16.3), $P < 0.001$), carbohydrate (3.76 (-22.0, 69.5) vs. -32.2 (-53.5, -8.70), $P < 0.01$), vitamin A (-23.2 (-93.8, 8.68) vs. -36.3 (-57.6, -8.45), $P < 0.01$), vitamin C (-10.4 (-27.9, 15.3) vs. -42.1 (-59.8, -17.1), $P < 0.001$), vitamin E (-18.4 (-110.0, 11.8) vs. -32.6 (-56.5, -3.86), $P < 0.01$), zinc (-7.86 (-26.9, 17.1) vs. -40.3 (-61.2, -9.09), $P < 0.001$). Indicated by D%, the differences in 24-hour recall of energy (26.3 (12.9, 48.2) vs. 40.8 (20.5, 63.1), $P < 0.001$), fat (30.4 (15.1, 69.5) vs. 40.8 (19.8, 58.7), $P < 0.001$), carbohydrate (29.6 (15.0, 71.3) vs. 40.1 (19.8, 56.7), $P < 0.01$), vitamin C (25.4 (14.0, 44.2) vs. 46.3 (29.0, 61.1), $P < 0.001$) and zinc (0.23 (0.12, 0.42) vs. 46.9 (22.3, 63.8), $P < 0.001$) were significantly lower than the difference in instant photography; while the difference in instant photography of calcium was significantly lower than that in 24-hour recall (30.8 (15.1, 90.3) vs. 0.46 (0.21, 0.62), $P < 0.001$).

Table 3 Correlation of nutrients data on 24-hour recall and instant photography with weighing method.

Type	n	24-hour recall		Instant photograph	
		r	p	r	p
Energy	287	0.909	< 0.001	0.838	< 0.001
Protein	287	0.890	< 0.001	0.898	< 0.001
Fat	287	0.915	< 0.001	0.940	< 0.001
Carbohydrate	287	0.743	< 0.001	0.919	< 0.001
Vitamin A	287	0.884	< 0.001	0.937	< 0.001
Vitamin C	287	0.871	< 0.001	0.970	< 0.001
Vitamin E	287	0.618	< 0.001	0.703	< 0.001
Ca	287	0.592	< 0.001	0.775	< 0.001
Fe	287	0.561	< 0.001	0.782	< 0.001
Zn	287	0.868	< 0.001	0.746	< 0.001

Table 4 Comparison on nutrients differences of 24-hour recall and instant photography with weighing method.

Type	n	Methods	d/g	D/g	d%	D%
Energy	287	24-hour	0.0001	15.0	0.01	26.3
		recall	(-13.6, 17.2)	(3.94, 38.7)	(-25.7, 27.6)	(12.9, 48.2)
		Instant photography	-11.8 (-43.7, 0.18)***	21.4 (8.34, 59.5)	-29.8 (-56.9, 0.98)***	40.8 (20.5, 63.1)***
Protein	287	24-hour	0.08	0.78	8.11	30.8
		recall	(-0.41, 2.97)	(0.28, 4.61)	(-21.7, 12.2)	(15.1, 121.9)
		Instant photography	-0.54 (-1.34, 0.01)***	0.83 (0.35, 1.95)	-26.5 (-53.5, 0.19)***	36.3 (16.7, 56.1)
Fat	287	24-hour	-0.0018	0.15	-0.74	30.4
		recall	(-0.09, 0.77)	(0.04, 2.00)	(-26.3, 58.0)	(15.1, 69.5)
		Instant photography	-0.0776 (-3.07, 0.71)***	0.17 (0.07, 0.67)	-23.86 (-53.5, 9.01)	40.8 (19.8, 58.7)***
Carbohydrate	287	24-hour	0.13	2.04	3.76	29.6
		recall	(-2.04, 2.05)	(0.57, 7.94)	(-22.0, 69.5)	(15.0, 71.3)
		Instant photography	-0.99 (-3.90, -0.11)***	1.45 (0.45, 5.44)***	-32.2 (-53.5, -8.70)***	40.1 (19.8, 56.7)***
Vitamin A	287	24-hour	-4.91	11.2	-23.2	35.8
		recall	(-16.4, 1.14)	(3.49, 30.3)	(-93.8, 8.68)	(15.8, 94.1)
		Instant photography	-6.33 (-18.2, -1.15)	9.88 (3.76, 23.3)	-36.3 (-57.6, -8.45)**	44.5 (23.2, 59.9)
Vitamin C	287	24-hour	-1.59	3.30	-10.4	25.4
		recall	(-5.43, 1.17)	(1.22, 7.53)	(-27.9, 15.3)	(14.0, 44.2)
		Instant photography	-5.43 (-15.1, 0.67)***	6.80 (1.80, 16.5)***	-42.1 (-59.8, -17.1)***	46.3 (29.0, 61.1)***
Vitamin E	287	24-hour	0.11	0.17	-18.4	34.0
		recall	(-0.35, 0.05)	(0.07, 0.49)	(-100.0, 11.8)	(15.1, 100.0)
		Instant photography	-0.11 (-0.40, -0.01)	0.19 (0.07, 0.46)	-32.6 (-56.5, -3.86)**	41.4 (19.4, 58.8)
Ca	287	24-hour	-3.18	5.73	-19.2	30.8
		recall	(-9.76, 1.26)	(2.58, 13.2)	(-66.7, 10.4)	(15.1, 90.3)
		Instant photography	-2.89 (-15.9, 3.26)	8.30 (3.00, 19.3)	0.21 (-0.53, 0.22)	0.46 (0.21, 0.62)***
Fe	287	24-hour	0.039	0.32	6.38	30.8
		recall	(-0.18, 1.54)	(0.11, 2.30)	(-21.7, 122.0)	(15.1, 122.0)
		Instant photography	-0.24 (-0.66, -0.05)***	0.36 (0.13, 0.81)	-36.5 (-55.9, -9.09)	43.8 (22.3, 57.6)
Zn	287	24-hour	-0.03	0.11	-7.86	0.23
		recall	(-0.16, 0.07)	(0.05, 0.31)	(-26.9, 17.1)	(0.12, 0.42)
		Instant photography	-0.13 (-0.46, -0.02)***	0.20 (0.06, 0.53)***	-40.3 (-61.2, -9.09)**	46.9 (22.3, 63.8)***

Data are expressed as median (interquartile range) according to the distribution of variables. ** $P < 0.01$ and *** $P < 0.001$ when compared with 24-hour recall method.

DISCUSSION

This study comes as a first insight to evaluate the validity of instant photography in college students. Instant photography showed a good estimation on foods weights and nutrients amount with weighing method. Compared with 24-hour recall, instant photography had more accurate estimations on fruits, egg and calcium. Even better, instant photography is neither burdensome nor time-consuming for the students, while easily feasible.

In nutrition and clinical research, a method of assessing dietary intake is declared valid when it measures actual intake over a specified period of time, with an acceptable level of accuracy compared to one or more criterion of measures. In other words, validity is not an “absolute” concept but a “relative” one [12]. Because the validity of a method is often determined by comparison, choosing the best reference or gold standard method is of paramount importance. In this study, weighing method as the golden standard method was used. Instant photography displayed a significant and valid correlation with the weighing method on food weights of grains, tubers, vegetables, fruits, meat and egg. 24-hour recall displayed a similar correlation with weighing method except fruits. Instant photography was also found to provide a good assessment of overall dietary nutrients amounts including energy, protein, fat, carbohydrate, vitamin A, vitamin C, calcium, iron and zinc (All $P < 0.001$). Other studies have also found a good correlation using the photography method in nutrient assessment [9,13,14].

Furthermore, we compared the difference between weighing and instant photograph with the difference between weighing and 24-hour recall on foods and nutrients data. Compared with the 24-hour recall, instant photograph displayed underestimations on food weights of grains, tubers, vegetables, meat, as well as nutrients amounts including energy, protein, carbohydrate, vitamin A, vitamin C, vitamin E and zinc. Several studies about the photographic method have also met with the underestimation problem [9,11,12,15-17,18,19]. The underestimation of food and nutrients may be due to some hidden part in the photographs, so making it difficult to estimate portion size. This is reason why instant photography had more accurate estimations on fruits and eggs. Thus, it is important for the photographer to separate foods before shooting and take pictures from different angles. The ability to accurately produce the perfect estimation rests on many factors, including quality of the photograph, the portion or size of the food item in regard to the food box, the background grid paper line and the camera angle. Furthermore, the process of estimation requires observers having a good degree of perception, conceptualization, and memory [20,21]. Therefore, more intensive training of the estimators is needed.

Instant photography method has gained attention and popularity around the world [22-24]. It is neither dependent on the participant's memory nor time-consuming, the accuracy in the estimation of instant photography method isn't affected by race, sex, age or education of the participants [25]. Therefore, the use of photography in dietary assessment has been found reliable and easy to use in a large-scale population [26-28]. Instant photography has further advantages in our study. Firstly, many studies have been conducted in controlled settings [9,11,29], our study was performed under normal living conditions. In a real-life situation, people serve themselves and eat what they give themselves. Participants were free to choose whatever they wanted to eat and to go on with their busy college schedule. Therefore, various food items were collected in our study. Secondly, we made use of a background grid paper to ease the estimation process. Portion size photographs as the reference were also pictured under the background of grid paper. Good inter-estimator agreement has been achieved in our study. It is important that developed image-assisted methods remain valid and accurate without being cumbersome or obtrusive for participants and investigators [17]. Thirdly, college students are used to smartphones, they appeared well prepared to use them to collect dietary data, making compliance better.

However, our study has some limitations. Firstly, our participants were not chosen randomly from the general population. All of our participants including trained estimators were medical students. This may explain the lesser underestimation seen in 24-hour recall compared with instant photography. Also, the effect of taking pictures by participants before and after eating may have helped them in 24h-recall. Secondly, portion size photographs didn't include all the foods eaten by participants. Estimators compared foods and portion sizes that may not be familiar to them, which may introduce errors. In order to objectively reduce underestimations and errors by instant photography, our future research interest is to apply artificial intelligence instead of human estimators to assess food weight.

CONCLUSION

Instant photography is a valid alternative method of dietary assessment in college students. This method is neither burdensome for the students nor time-consuming, while easily feasible.

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